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Supplementary material (B) for: A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with Prolog

Mikel Vandeloise

University of Namur, Belgium

Namur Digital Institute

(e-mail: mikel.vandeloise@student.unamur.be)

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Abstract

This supplementary material extends foundational research on programming paradigms to include a detailed analysis of typing systems, compilation techniques, memory management, and error handling mechanisms. We introduce the Typing System Collaboration Metric (TCM), the Metric for Collaboration between Compilation Systems (MCC), and the Collaboration Metric for Memory and Error Management (MCEM). These tools collectively provide a framework for assessing the interoperability of programming languages within software development projects. This supplementary material aims to furnish developers with the insights needed for selecting and integrating diverse programming technologies effectively, thereby supporting efficient multi-language software development.

KEYWORDS: Supplementary Material, Programming Language Interoperability, Typing Systems, Compilation Techniques, Memory Management Systems, Error Handling, Software Development Metrics, Multi-Language Programming Environments.

1 Introduction

In an increasingly interconnected software development landscape, the ability of diverse programming languages to coexist and interact within composite environments is crucial. Building upon the foundational work presented in our earlier study (Vandeloise et al. 2024), which introduced a taxonomy of programming paradigms and their interactions, this supplementary material extends our research to explore additional critical dimensions: typing systems, compilation techniques, memory management, and error handling mechanisms. This comprehensive approach deepens our understanding of programming languages and enhances their interoperability in multi-language development projects (Scott 2000).

For typing systems, we elaborate on a six-dimensional tuple encapsulating the nature, strength, mode, inference level, and supports for graduated and duck typing. This granular analysis enables the creation of the Typing System Collaboration Metric (TCM), which quantifies the compatibility of typing systems across languages, providing a score

from zero (no compatibility) to one (full compatibility). This metric builds on our previously established metrics for paradigm compatibility, adding a new layer of depth to the assessment of language integration. The robustness of such metrics draws on established methods in software metrics, emphasizing their relevance in practical and academic contexts (Fenton and Bieman 2014).

Similarly, we introduce a systematic evaluation of compilation systems, defining modes (compiled, interpreted, or both) and the incorporation of Just-In-Time (JIT) or Ahead-Of-Time (AOT) compilation techniques. The practical implications of these techniques are well exemplified in high-performance environments such as Oracle’s Java platform, which utilizes JIT compilation to enhance execution efficiency (Oracle 2023). The Metric for Collaboration between Compilation Systems (MCC) complements our earlier paradigm-based metrics by evaluating the technological and procedural compatibilities that influence language performance and integration capabilities. Insights into the effectiveness of these compilation strategies are supported by the comprehensive works of Cooper and Torczon (Cooper and Torczon 2022), Aho, Lam, Sethi and Ullman (Aho et al. 2007) and Muchnick (Muchnick 1997), which provide a foundation for understanding advanced compilation techniques and their implications for language performance.

Furthermore, the study explores memory and error management systems—areas critical to the operational efficiency and reliability of software applications. Through a detailed metric, the Collaboration Metric for Memory and Error Management (MCEM), we assess the effectiveness of different languages’ strategies in managing runtime resources and handling errors, essential aspects for modern computing applications. This exploration is underpinned by contemporary compiler design insights from Grune et al. (Grune et al. 2012), which emphasize the significance of memory management in modern software environments.

This supplementary material integrates with and significantly expands the scope of our initial research, providing tools for a more holistic assessment of programming languages’ interoperability. By combining insights from both studies, we offer a robust framework that aids developers in choosing compatible technologies and supports academic advancements in software engineering. This rigorous, multifaceted approach ensures that the research meets practical development needs and enriches the theoretical constructs of computer science, paving the way for future innovations in the field.

2 Formalisation of typing systems

A typing system, denoted S , can formally be defined as a tuple of six elements, i.e. $S = (T, F, N, I, G, D)$, where each element represents a specific dimension of the system:

- T represents the nature of typing as **Static**, **Dynamic**, **Gradual**.
- F represents the strength of the typing as **Strong**, **Weak**.
- N represents the set of typing modes, such as **{Nominal, Structural}**.
- I represents the levels of type inference such as **None**, **Partial**, **Complete**.
- G is a Boolean indicator of graduated typing support.
- D is a boolean indicator of duck typing support.

Formally defining a typing system as a six-dimensional tuple has several advantages. This approach provides a thorough understanding of typing systems, facilitates their analysis and comparison, and encourages research and innovation in this crucial area of computer science. In addition, it provides a common language for communication and collaboration between researchers and practitioners, contributing to the advancement of typing science.

Definition 1

The Typing System Collaboration Metric (TCM) is defined, for two typing systems $S_1 = (T_1, F_1, N_1, I_1, G_1, D_1)$ and $S_2 = (T_2, F_2, N_2, I_2, G_2, D_2)$, as

$$TCM(S_1, S_2) = \alpha \times C_T(T_1, T_2) + \beta \times C_F(F_1, F_2) + \gamma \times C_N(N_1, N_2) \\ + \delta \times C_I(I_1, I_2) + \epsilon \times C_G(G_1, G_2) + \zeta \times C_D(D_1, D_2)$$

$$\text{where } : \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \epsilon, \zeta \in [0, 1] \wedge \alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta + \epsilon + \zeta = 1$$

The coefficients α , β , γ , δ , ϵ , and ζ are weights assigned to the different factors of the metric, and they must reflect the relative importance of each aspect in the collaboration between the typing systems.

This formula provides an overall compatibility score between the typing systems of two programming languages, considering the nature of the typing, the strength of the typing, nominal or structural typing, the level of type inference, support for graded typing and support for duck typing. The score ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates full compatibility between typing systems, and 0 indicates no compatibility.

Nature of typing (C_T)

$$C_T(T_1, T_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } T_1 = T_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_T(T_1, T_2)$ compares the nature of two types T_1 and T_2 . This function is useful for determining whether two types are identical in terms of static, dynamic or gradual typing.

Typing strength

$$C_F(F_1, F_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } F_1 = F_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_F(F_1, F_2)$ compares the typing strength of two types F_1 and F_2 . This function is useful for determining whether two types are identical in terms of strong or weak typing.

Nominal or structural typing (C_N)

$$C_N(N_1, N_2) = \frac{|N_1 \cap N_2|}{|N_1 \cup N_2|}$$

The function $C_N(N_1, N_2)$ compares the nominal and structural typing of two types N_1 and N_2 . This function is useful for determining the similarity between two types based on their structure and their names.

Type inference (C_I)

$$C_I(I_1, I_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } I_1 = I_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_I(I_1, I_2)$ compares the level of type inference provided by two typing systems I_1 and I_2 . This function is useful for determining whether two typing systems infer in the same way (none, partial or complete).

Support for graduated typing (C_G)

$$C_G(G_1, G_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } G_1 = G_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_G(G_1, G_2)$ compares the support of the graded typing of two types G_1 and G_2 . This function is useful for determining whether two typing systems support graduated typing in the same way (present or absent).

Support for duck typing (C_D)

$$C_D(D_1, D_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } D_1 = D_2 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_D(D_1, D_2)$ compares the Duck Typing support of two typing systems D_1 and D_2 . This function is useful for determining whether two typing systems support Duck Typing in the same way (present or absent).

This formal approach makes it possible to systematically compare and evaluate the typing systems of programming languages. Using this metric, developers, language designers and researchers can identify key similarities and differences between typing systems, making it easier to understand the implications of using different languages for specific projects. In addition, it can help anticipate potential challenges when integrating languages with different typing systems into the same development environment.

Table 1: Programming languages typing systems

Language	Typing nature	Typing strength	Nom/Struc	Type inference	Gradual typing	Duck typing
XML	-	-	-	-	-	-
Scheme	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
ML	Static	Strong	Nominal	Complete	No	No
Prolog	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
CLP	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
LIFE	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
AKL	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
Oz	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Complete	No	Yes
Alice	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Complete	No	Yes
Curry	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Complete	No	Yes
Haskell	Static	Strong	Nominal	Complete	No	No
E	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
CLU	Static	Strong	Nominal	Partial	No	No
OCaml	Static	Strong	Structural	Complete	No	No
Erlang	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
Pascal	Static	Strong	Nominal	None	No	No
C	Static	Strong	Nominal	None	No	No
SNOBOL	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
Icon	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes
Java	Static	Strong	Nominal	Partial	No	No
C++	Static	Strong	Nominal	Partial	No	No
Smalltalk	Dynamic	Weak	Both	Partial	No	Yes

The data presented in this table has not yet undergone all the necessary checks to guarantee its accuracy. As a result, we cannot guarantee its accuracy and reliability. Consequently, we cannot accept any responsibility for the use or re-use of this data. We invite you to use them with caution and to always carry out your checks before using them in a decision-making context.

3 Formalisation of compilation systems

A compilation system, denoted C , can formally be defined as a tuple of three elements, i.e. $C = (M, J, A)$, where each element represents a specific dimension of the compilation system:

- M represents the set of compilation modes, where $M = \text{"Compiled"}, \text{"Interpreted"}, \text{"Both"}$.
- J is a Boolean indicator of the use of JIT compilation.
- A is a Boolean indicator of the use of AOT compilation.

Definition 2

The Metric for Collaboration between Compilation Systems (MCC) is defined, for two compilation systems $C_{L_1} = (M_1, J_1, A_1)$ and $C_{L_2} = (M_2, J_2, A_2)$, as

$$MCC(C_{L_1}, C_{L_2}) = \alpha \times C_M(M_1, M_2) + \beta \times C_J(J_1, J_2) + \gamma \times C_A(A_1, A_2)$$

$$\text{where } : \alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1] \wedge \alpha + \beta + \gamma = 1$$

The coefficients α , β , and γ are weights assigned to the various factors in the metric, and they must be strictly between 0 and 1 and adjusted to reflect the relative importance of each aspect in the collaboration between compilation systems.

This formula provides an overall compatibility score between the compilation systems of two programming languages, considering the compilation mode, the use of JIT, and the use of AOT. The score ranges from 0 to 1, where 1 indicates total compatibility between the compilation systems, and 0 indicates no compatibility.

Compilation method (C_M)

$$C_M(M_1, M_2) = \frac{|M_1 \cap M_2|}{|M_1 \cup M_2|}$$

The function $C_M(M_1, M_2)$ compares the compilation mode of two programming languages M_1 and M_2 , considering the intersection of compilation methods.

JIT compilation (C_J)

$$C_J(J_1, J_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } J_1 = J_2, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_J(J_1, J_2)$ is used to compare the Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation support of two programming languages J_1 and J_2 . This function is useful for determining whether the two languages support JIT compilation in the same way (present or absent).

AOT compilation (C_A)

$$C_A(A_1, A_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } A_1 = A_2, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

The function $C_A(A_1, A_2)$ compares the Ahead-Of-Time (AOT) compilation support of two programming languages A_1 and A_2 . This function is useful for determining whether the two languages support AOT compilation in the same way (present or absent).

This rigorous formalisation of compilation systems for programming languages proposes a systematic method for assessing their compatibility through the Metric of Collaboration between Compilation systems (MCC). Based on mathematically defined criteria such as compile mode, JIT support and AOT support, this approach enables IT players, developers, language designers and researchers, to meticulously examine the similarities and differences between compiler systems. This precise and objective analysis helps to navigate the complex landscape of language interoperability, facilitating the selection of technologies for various projects and anticipating the challenges of integration into multi-language development environments.

Table 2: Compilation modes of programming languages

Language	Compilation mode	JIT compilation	AOT compilation
Scheme	Both	Yes	Yes
ML	Compiled	No	Yes
Prolog	Both	Yes	Yes
CLP	Both	Yes	Yes
LIFE	Both	Yes	Yes
AKL	Both	Yes	Yes
Oz	Both	Yes	Yes
Alice	Compiled	No	Yes
Curry	Both	Yes	Yes
Haskell	Compiled	No	Yes
E	Both	Yes	Yes
CLU	Compiled	No	Yes
OCaml	Compiled	No	Yes
Erlang	Both	Yes	Yes
Pascal	Compiled	No	Yes
C	Compiled	No	Yes
SNOBOL	Interpreted	No	No
Icon	Interpreted	No	No
Java	Both	Yes	Yes
C++	Compiled	No	Yes
Smalltalk	Interpreted	Yes	No

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4 Formalisation of memory and error management systems

A memory management system, denoted GM , is formalised by a tuple of two elements, namely $GM = (M, SGM)$, where :

- M represents the set of memory management modes, where $M = \{\text{GC, Manual}\}$.
- SGM represents the specific memory management strategies, where $SGM = \{\text{None, Counting References, Generational, Incremental}\}$.

An error management system, denoted GE , is defined by a tuple of two elements, namely $GE = (E, SGE)$, where :

- E represents the set of error handling mechanisms, where $E = \{\text{Exceptions, Error Codes}\}$.
- SGE indicates the set of specific error management strategies, where $SGE = \{\text{None, Assertions, Design Contracts, Formal Verification}\}$.

Definition 3

The Collaboration Metric for Memory and Error Management (MCEM) is defined, for two systems $G_{M_{L_1}} = (M_1, SGM_1)$ and $G_{E_{L_2}} = (E_2, SGE_2)$, as

$$MCEM(G_{M_{L_1}}, G_{E_{L_2}}) = \alpha \times C_M(M_1, M_2) + \beta \times C_{SGM}(SGM_1, SGM_2) + \gamma \times C_E(E_1, E_2) + \delta \times C_{SGE}(SGE_1, SGE_2)$$

$$\text{where: } \alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta \in [0, 1] \wedge \alpha + \beta + \gamma + \delta = 1$$

The coefficients α , β , γ , and δ are weights assigned to the different factors of the metric. They must be strictly between 0 and 1 and adjusted to reflect the relative importance of each aspect in the collaboration between memory and error management systems.

This formula calculates an overall compatibility score between the memory and error management systems of two programming languages, considering memory management strategies, error management and their specificities. The score can vary from 0 to 1, where 1 means total compatibility and 0 means no compatibility.

Memory management mode (C_M)

$$C_M(M_1, M_2) = \frac{|M_1 \cap M_2|}{|M_1 \cup M_2|}$$

This function evaluates the compatibility of memory management modes between two programming languages by measuring the intersection over the union of the mode sets.

Specific Memory Management Strategies (C_{SGM})

$$C_{SGM}(SGM_1, SGM_2) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } SGM_1 = SGM_2, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Evaluates whether the two programming languages share the same memory management strategy.

Error Management (C_E)

$$C_E(E_1, E_2) = \frac{|E_1 \cap E_2|}{|E_1 \cup E_2|}$$

Compares approaches to error handling (exceptions, error codes) between two programming languages using the intersection measure on union.

Specific Error Management Strategies (C_{SGE})

$$C_{SGE}(SGE_1, SGE_2) = \frac{|SGE_1 \cap SGE_2|}{|SGE_1 \cup SGE_2|}$$

This function calculates the compatibility between the advanced error handling supported by two programming languages.

These functions provide a mathematically rigorous basis for assessing the compatibility of programming languages in terms of their memory and error management. This analysis identifies important similarities and differences that can influence the integration and collaboration between different languages in a multi-language development environment.

Table 3: Memory and error management in programming languages

Language	Memory management	Memory management strategy	Error handling	Advanced error handling
Scheme	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Formal verification
ML	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Design by contract
Prolog	Hybrid	Reference counting	Both	Assertions
CLP	Hybrid	Reference counting	Both	Assertions
LIFE	Hybrid	Reference counting	Exceptions	Assertions
AKL	Hybrid	Reference counting	Exceptions	Assertions
Oz	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Formal verification
Alice	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Design by contract
Curry	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Formal verification
Haskell	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Design by contract
E	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Formal verification
CLU	Manual	None	Exceptions	Assertions
OCaml	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Design by contract
Erlang	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Formal verification
Pascal	Manual	None	Exceptions	Assertions
C	Manual	None	Error codes	None
SNOBOL	Manual	None	Exceptions	None
Icon	Manual	None	Exceptions	None
Java	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions, Design by contract
C++	Manual	None	Exceptions	Assertions
Smalltalk	GC	Generational	Exceptions	Assertions

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5 Conclusion

This supplementary material has systematically addressed the interoperability of programming languages through detailed metrics assessing typing systems, compilation techniques, memory management, and error handling mechanisms. We introduced the Typing System Collaboration Metric (TCM), Metric for Collaboration between Compilation Systems (MCC), and Collaboration Metric for Memory and Error Management (MCEM) as formal tools to evaluate and enhance compatibility across diverse programming environments. By extending foundational work in programming paradigms to include practical and measurable aspects, this supplementary material contributes to the technical literature with rigorous evaluation tools. These contributions are intended to assist developers and researchers in making informed decisions regarding technology integration in software development environments.

References

- AHO, A. V., LAM, M. S., AND ULLMAN, J. D. 2007. *Compilers Principles, Techniques & Tools*. Pearson Education.
- COOPER, K. D. AND TORCZON, L. 2022. *Engineering a Compiler*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- FENTON, N. AND BIEMAN, J. 2014. *Software Metrics: A Rigorous and Practical Approach*. CRC Press.
- GRUNE, D., VAN REEUWIJK, K., BAL, H. E., JACOBS, C. J., AND LANGENDOEN, K. 2012. *Modern Compiler Design*. Springer Science & Business Media.
- MUCHNICK, S. 1997. *Advanced Compiler Design Implementation*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- ORACLE. Accessed 2023. The java language environment. Online.
- SCOTT, M. 2000. *Programming Language Pragmatics*. Morgan Kaufmann.
- VANDELOISE, M., YERNAUX, G., AND VANHOOF, W. 2024. A metric approach to paradigmatic collaboration: case study with prolog. Tech. rep., University of Namur, Namur Digital Institute, Namur, Belgium.